

Religious Tolerance Politics and Digital Economy in Nigeria

Silas Sarkes Wankir PhD

Department of Christian Religious Studies, School of Arts and Social Sciences, Federal College of Education
Pankshin, Plateau State, Nigeria

Abstract

Religious tolerance is one among the essential elements for peaceful coexistence in any pluralistic society. It is the basis for social stability and integration that shapes the environment for the game of politics. Hence for any human society to enjoy peaceful and harmonious relations, religious tolerance has to be well understood, preached and upheld by all members of the society. Intolerance of religious feelings and values has led to bloody wars, division of states and nations. Nigeria as a multi ethnic and multi faith nation has become enmeshed in a tangle of religious intolerance as a result of political unrest, ethnic prejudice, and youth restiveness religious bigotry and extremism, and other social vices. These waves of social vices constitute a great obstacle to flourishing political and digital economic development in Nigeria. Hence in pursuance of a peaceful and conducive atmosphere for a healthy political and digital economic development, and all facet of life, this paper examines the meaning of religious tolerance, politics and digital economy. The paper discussed forgiveness, reconciliation, justice and interfaith dialogue as basic ingredients that help in the promotion of religious tolerance it also discovered that lack of adequate knowledge and proper understanding of other people's religion is the main cause of religious intolerance. The paper concluded by recommending that religious tolerance education should be incorporated into the curricular of all levels of Nigeria's educational system.

Keywords: Religious Tolerance, Politics, and Digital Economy.

Introduction

Diversity is central to the identity of the Nigerian nation. People from different religions, creeds and affiliations have come together to create a nation that is widely identified as a melting pot of humanity. Hence, Nigeria is a multi-ethnic and multi-religious country with great potentials for rapid growth and development. In short, Nigeria is a model pluralistic society, with people of different faiths, ethnic groups, levels of education and multiple differences living together. Nigeria is endowed with a lot of human, materials and other mineral resources. The size of the nation is an advantage too, which if properly explored, could place a highly respectable position in the midst of any group of nation in the world. But these have not been put to the best use, because of insatiable desire for the accumulation of wealth, glorification of corruption as a way of life, indifference about morality, justice and fair play, lack of correct orientation and attitude especially in matters of interpersonal and communal relations, and importantly in the relationship between man and God. Values that lead to religious tolerance such as accountability, commitment to duties, love of ones neighbor as one self, selflessness and generosity are in many cases not taken seriously by many people.

Yet, with common access to amenities, resources, markets and generally the Nigerian livelihood, there is need to find a working model of cooperation, tolerance, understanding and faith in the Nigerian society that will lead towards a prosperous and harmonious development. This paper therefore considers the importance of political and religious tolerance to foster an economy that is increasingly becoming digital. It also sees the digital economy as a tool to further foster community, this is majorly because one of the things that keep the Nigerian society hopeful of its continued unity is the trade that brings people together. Today, with the aid of an increasingly digitalized economy, Nigerians of different persuasions are cooperating in e-trade, e-commerce, e-negotiations and e-delivery of goods and services.

Conceptual Clarifications

Religious Tolerance

Religious tolerance is the acceptance, respect and accommodating of diverse religious beliefs, practices and traditions within a society. It involves creating an atmosphere where people of different religions backgrounds can peacefully coexist, without fear of discrimination or persecuting in the environment, thereby giving each his/her freedom to practice their faith without interference or harm (The Nigeria Inter-religions Council (NIREC)).¹ Religious tolerance is the possible and practicable cordial relationship that exist between religions in a society. It means the peaceful coexistence among the adherents of different religions especially in a given society. It also means providing a common ground on which diverse religious groups can meet see one another in mutual respect and sharing. It is a way of knowing people of other religions and understand their perspectives on various issues and to explore one mountain (God) through many paths.

Akmal, Akhmedovich, and Laylo, Sadrievna² avow that the implementation of religious tolerance requires the following measures: Ensuring full freedom of religious and conscience, Act on the basis of a deep understanding of the logical content of the ideas put forward by religious. Recognition of the equality of different religions and denominations. Ensure that different religions and denominations treat each other with mutual respect. Introduction of the practice of respect for religion and spiritual values. Creating conditions for all religions to live in cooperation and harmony. Prevent the forced assimilation of religious view. Ensuring the equal participation of all believers in the political process as citizens. Prevent the use of religion for subversive purposes by forming religious parties. Respect for religious feelings of believers. Prevent persecution of believers. The idea of religious tolerance implies cooperation of not only believers, but all members of society in the cause of goodness and in an important condition for strengthening peace and stability.

Politics

Politics is the study of the government. That is, a collection of officers who make, interpret and enforce rules for the entire community. Tella, A. and Omotayo, A.M.³ politics is all the activities, actions and policies that relate to the governance and administration of a nation. It involves the decision making processes, the formation of policies and the exercise of power to guide and direct a country's affairs. Power is necessary in politics to generate progress and development just like power is necessary in electricity to generate light. Politics can also be viewed as the process of deciding who gets what, when and how. Politics is a sphere of purposeful behavior through which we seek to live better than we do now. Despite the difference in definitions there is a common ground in the centrality of the state and power to the political process (Emoghene, Aghoho Kalvin, and Okolie, Ugo Chuks).⁴ Thus, politics is concentrated as revolving round the state, its agencies, and activities and overall impact on the society and also it an analysis of government and its responsibilities. Politics as it concerns religious tolerance involves all the roles that government and the political actors perform in promoting protecting and enforcing religious freedom and ensuring the equal treatment of the individual(s) irrespective of their religious beliefs. Government have the power to shape and enforce policies that help to promote religious freedom that ensures equal rights of all the citizens.

Digital Economy

It is important to establish that hitherto there is no universal consensus on the actual definition of what digital economy is. This is because definitions are always a reflection of the times, and trends from which they emerge. However, the World Bank group, defines digital economy as the economics of activities that are based on digital technologies such as information and communication technologies (ICT). This involves the production, distribution and consumption of goods and services facilitated by digital platforms, networks and technologies. In other words it encompasses the use of the internet, mobile devices, social media and other digital tools to create economic values. In other words, digital economy refers to the use of technologies in various economic activities, such as buying and selling of goods services, conducting financial transactions

and offering online platform for business. It entails using the internet, mobile devices, social media, and other digital tools to create economic benefits. Nguyen, Oliver⁵ opine that Digital economy refers to the use of information technology to create, adapt, market and consume goods and services that are based on the use of information technology; in order to make money. Digital economy refers to the economic activity that results from billions of online connections that occur every between people, business, devices, data and processes.

Religion, Politics and the Nigerian Experience

According to Yahya, Muslih Tayo,⁶ there are erring tendencies in the practice of religion in Nigeria which usually affect interfaith relations negatively and pose threat to peaceful coexistence. Such tendencies are indeed the reasons why the nation has not been able to attain her development goals. They are found in areas of misguided approach to proselyzation, manipulation of religion for selfish ends, ignorant misinterpretation of teaching of religion (by Adherents of the religion and non-adherents of it) and neglect the teachings on crucial issues of interfaith relations. Yahya, Muslih Tayo⁷ further adds that the misunderstanding of interfaith relations leads to mutual suspicion and unhealthy rivalry especially between Muslim and Christian groups in Nigeria, which unfortunately has turned religion to a ready tool in the hands of mischief makers in many parts of the country. The sponsors of violence and vandalism who claim to be religious are certainly not carrying out such atrocities in the service of religion or in other to establish the will of God. Some people who seek political position often exploit peoples' commitment and royalty to religion, to whip up sentiment in other to recognized as leaders 2014 As a result, misunderstanding and ignorance have led to mutual suspicion and mistrust in human life, which has led to various conflict and bloody disagreements in Nigeria. People are hostile to what they do not know, causing injuries to people hearts. Presently, the hearts of Nigerians are carrying wounds caused by religions sentiments. People don't value human lives, people are carried away by the pursuit for increase in population of the adherents of faiths to the detriment of religions tolerant and economic develop

Similarly, politics today in Nigeria is a "do or die" affair, the struggle for political power and control at the Centre has over heated the nations politic and created unnecessary tension which has resulted to bigotry among religions. Political things are recruited and armed by these same politicians who at the end of the day loose grip of these things and these arms are used on defenseless citizens. The current democratic dispensation since inception has been besieged with unprecedented vice disturbance and social insecurity resulting in massive destruction of lives and property. The religious and ethnic dimension of these upheavals makes them a serious threat to national security. Kidnapping and all forms of maladies, military group exist in all geo political zones resulting to a lot of bloodshed, social and economic dislocation and its attendant poverty, insecurity and unemployment.

The Place of Religion in the Constitution of Nigeria

The preamble of the Nigerian constitution reads thus;

"we the people of the federal republic of Nigeria having firmly and solemnly resolved, to live in unity and harmony as one in risible and indissoluble sovereign nation under god, dedicated to the promotion of inter African society, word and peace international cooperation and understanding and to provide for a constitution for the purpose of promoting good government and welfare of all person in our country on the principle of freedom, equality and justice, and for the purpose of consolidating the unity of our people, do hereby make, enact and give our self the constitution."

From this preamble, one understands that the constitution of Nigeria calls for integration irrespective of language barrier, religion or sex. Hence the constitution is a tool that binds Nigerians together. This section of the constitution has to do with freedom of worship. Other areas of the constitution spelt it out that; the membership of any political parties in Nigeria shall be open to all citizens of the country irrespective of his/her place of origin, religion or ethnic group. The constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria does not ignore or

opposes the existence of religion, instead, it accepts the existence of religious plurality in the country. But all she is saying is that government shall not be responsible for sponsoring or payment of any religious organization.

Obstacles that Impede Religious Tolerance in Nigeria

Obstacles that impede religious tolerance in Nigeria include:

- i. **Poverty:** A significant recipe that causes religious tolerance is poverty. A hungry man, they say, is an angry man who can vent his anger on anything. The levels of poverty in Nigeria today constitute a great threat to the citizens, particularly when many people cannot afford needs like shelter, clothing and feeding. Sarkes, Silas⁸ lamented that the present condition of living in Nigeria is hard for the average citizens. Eating poses a real problem, not to mention taking family members to the hospitals. Many families can no longer pay school fees. There is no job for even those who have graduated from secondary schools, Polytechnics, Colleges of Education and Universities. The Nigerian masses are suffering economic deprivation in the form of exploitation. Hence, poverty creates a condition of desperation, frustration, tension and hopelessness. With the present situation, people tend not to tolerate one another.
- ii. **Unemployment:-** The rate of unemployment have been on the increase over the years in Nigeria, which translates that as more and more people join the labor force more jobs are not created to cater for them. Plateau resolve⁹ maintained that lack of job opportunities and the growing rate of unemployed youths have aggravated religious intolerance in plateau state and the country at large. Segun, Joshua. and Jegede, Ajibade Ebenezer¹⁰ equally aligned to this fact that poverty, unemployment and underemployment, especially among youth is a contributory factor to religious intolerance.
- iii. **Ignorance:-** The holy Bible says “My people are destroyed for lack of knowledge” (Hosea 4:6^a). When people are illiterate or lack knowledge, they are easy to be manipulated, indoctrinated and brain wash. Hence, when people lack the knowledge about religion belief and practice they welcome or buy every form of idea giving to them without questionings they lack critical rational thought. For example, a lot of Muslims have misconceptions on a number of things about Christianity. The same happens with Christians about Islam or Muslim. This misconceptions are responsible for religious intolerance. Similarly, the standard of western education civilization among the adherents of Christianity, Islam and Traditional religion worshipers have continued to be a threat to religious tolerance because one is thinking that the other will one day take the mantle of political leadership over the other.
- iv. **The Manipulation of Religion:** To day in Nigeria, religion has been used, abused, misused by political elite for their selfish interest. People these days no more tolerate one another because politicians have divided them base on religion and ethnic line to gain their heart desire. The manipulation of religion assumed dangerous dimensions in the political and social relationship in Nigeria. Thus, the abuse of religion through it manipulation has created condition for agitation, allegation of alienation, suspicion, neglect and marginalization. Unfortunately, as a result, some so-called clerics of Christianity and Islam, despite their callings are giving to selfishness. They employed fowls means to perpetrate religious intolerance knowing that they will be invited by the government in power to seek their consent in that way, they get classer to the government for their personal interest.
- v. **Mass Media:** The primary function of the media is to inform, educate and to entertain the people. Information obtained from the press is far more reaching as it gets to as many people as possible within a very short time. The press is also noted for shaping people opinions. But when wrong information is rolled out to the public, the catastrophic effect cannot be under estimated. For example, the media that is in support of one religion than the other will give a favorable report than the other. And when this happen, whole things will become aggravated as a misinformation relayed on the air which than be lead to religious intolerance.¹¹

- vi. Government at all level in Nigeria:** Has become a major player of religion in order to achieve her goal. In the most case, government has been accused of partisanship. Government partisanship with religion show itself in various ways. They include attendance of religious programs, and sponsor of project, biased religious patronage to the exclusion of others, used of religion to silence grievance or protest and religion corruption. Government partnership toward religious groups in Nigeria is a sustained features which create bitterness, acrimony, suspension and apprehension between Christian and Muslims over the year in Nigeria.¹²
- vii. Collapse of Religious and Society Values:** According to Obilom, Joseph Nigeria is presently experiencing what could be called crises of decay or collapse of religious and societal values.”¹³ Such values include, integrity, commitment to service, accountability and sanity of life. Despite the various religious claims, practical religious life that will help to affect good governance and responsible leadership is still a mirage in Nigeria. As a result, Nigerians have lost the value of brotherliness as most people have become selfish and wickedness has increased. Love and compassion which Christianity and Islam preach have been lost. The love for the neighbor which Christianity and Islam teach has been abandoned. Instead, what we have today in Nigerian is brother fighting against brother, sister against sister and war of reprisals.

FACTORS THAT PROMOTE RELIGIOUS AND POLITICAL TOLERANCE

Religious tolerance entails mutual harmony and peaceful relation between various religious group and people in Nigeria. Hence to promote mutual harmony and peaceful relations, the following factors have been identified:

- i. **Forgiveness:** This one among the recipe that help in promoting religious tolerance. Forgiveness is to pardon a person for an offence he/she committed. When the offender realized that what he/she has done and ask to be pardoned, he/she can be granted forgiveness. By so doing, it helps in the bringing about unity, friendship and happiness which are basic ingredients of religious tolerance. Kaigama, Ignatius says that for Nigeria to achieve a healthy nation there must be forgiveness and justice to promote religious tolerance.¹⁴ Without forgiveness heaven will be empty.¹⁵
- ii. **Justice:** This means giving to each he/her due. It is the fair and proper administration of the societal laws. Ekpenyong, Obo maintain that justice is a pillar in religious tolerance where it enhance respect for other people right, positions, allocation appointment and avoidance of sharp practices. With justice, the fundamental human right of each religion are not trampled upon with impurity. Nobody is seen as a sacred cow because the rule of law have effect on anybody.¹⁶ Also, Njoku, Nkechi and Njoku, Donatus agree that justice guarantees proportionate and equitable distribution of the natural wealth among multi ethnic and multi religious group for co-existence.¹⁷
- iii. **Reconciliation:** This is the process by which an individual bring back or restore good relationship that has broking by conflict or violence. Reconciliation consist of restoration and healing. It encourage the individual to acknowledge the past, confess former wrongs, relieve the experience under safe condition, mourn the losses, validate the experience pain and grief receive empathy and support and restore broken relationship. Reconciliation create a space where forgiveness can be offered and accepted for unity, co-operation and tolerance. Reconciliation help to eliminate all the barriers create by human selfishness, greed, ethnicity, tribalism, racism and leave no room for enmity, hatred, prejudice, discrimination, bias. It establish a friendly relationship between people who are at variance with each other and readmit one another.¹⁸
- iv. **Interfaith Dialogue:** This is another significant recipe in promoting religious tolerance. Inter faith dialogue provide a platform where individual from different religious background come together and engage in open and respectful discussion. Dialogue help to foster mutual understanding and building bridge between religions. When there is religious encounter at the level of practical sincerity reciprocity,

it will promote religious tolerance. Arinze, Francis define interfaith dialogue as a meeting of people differing religion in an atmosphere of freedom and openness, in order to listening to the other, to try to the other, to try to understand that person's religion, and hopeful to seek possibilities of collaboration.¹⁹

- v. **Institution of Learning:** This can also help in promoting religious tolerance. This can be done through organizing workshop, seminars and awareness campaigns to educate people about different religions, their beliefs and practices.
- vi. A robust legal system that protect religious freedom and ensure equal right for all religious groups is importance for the promotion of religious tolerance.
Religious and political tolerance are also base on the universal declaration of human right whose thrust is to promote tolerance among people as they live together.

Tolerance and the Digital Economy in Nigeria

For the growth of digital economy in Nigeria, tolerance is significant in promoting a conducive and cooperative atmosphere where people of different religious background can contribute and benefit from digital advancement. Tolerance creates an environment for innovation and collaboration in the digital economy. This is because when individuals from different religious background come together, it creates opportunities for collaboration and giving the individuals equal chances and freedom of expression of their ideas, thoughts, expertise and giving them insights and approaches to problem solving that leads to development and economic growth. Tolerance promotes creativity in the digital sector. When people from diverse religious background project and respect their diversity, they can bring about unique perspectives, experiences and cultural insights that would lead to development of digital products and services. Religious tolerance supports entrepreneurship in the digital economy. This help the individuals to start and manage their business. By doing so, it creates job opportunities and economic growth.

Religious tolerance helps in the development of ethical digital practices. This is because values such as fairness, honest, accountability, humility, sense of humour are often taught by various religious. The development of such attitudes guides the individuals and their businesses in the digital economy. This in turns promote trust and integrity, which are basic ingredients for the growth and sustainability of digital economy. By embracing religious tolerance, it enhances social cohesion and helps in removing barriers, prejudice and biases thereby giving way to faster and environment where people from different religious background can participate in digital market places, access opportunities and contribute their quota to economic development. Religious tolerance encourages equal access to digital services and opportunities irrespective of one's religious beliefs. This inclusiveness enables the individuals to get the necessary knowledge and skills in digital economy. The access to digital service foster initiatives that filled the gaps in digital work and gives access to technology and digital literacy.

Similarly Religious tolerance can use digital platforms to promote interfaith dialogue and understanding thereby creating a conducive environment for digital economy. The digital market space is becoming more and more like the common markets that were common in Nigeria before political and religious crises made them segregated spaces. While intolerance has led to separation of markets into political, economic and religious no-go-areas, the digital space is reuniting people of different ethnic groups, social classes, religious persuasions and economic backgrounds to seek goods and services from each other. The potential is great and must be used in the two-way service of enhancing tolerance and promoting the digital economy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, with the recent happenings in Nigeria, it seems more than necessary that this paper have addressed religious tolerance, politics and digital economy. The paper discussed tolerance and openness to diversity as a crucial element for the adoption and generation of new ideas. Hence, the level of scientific knowledge, tolerance and diversity are conducive for technological creativity and innovation. A series of

factors have been identified to the causes of religious and political intolerance, especially in a multi ethnic and political settings. The paper found the causes to include: poverty, unemployment, ignorance, manipulation of religion, mass media among others. Similarly, the paper discussed some factors that promote religious and political tolerance to include: forgiveness, justice, reconciliation, interfaith dialogue and many others.

Endnotes

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